

Pedagogical Research and Development

Volume: 3 Issue: 1

2024

ISSN: 2791-3627

 KMF PUBLISHERS

<http://kmf-publishers.com/prd/>

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo>.

Pedagogical Research and Development

REVIEW
ARTICLE**OPEN ACCESS**

Freely available online

Received: 11 January 2024

Accepted: 26 March 2024

Corresponding author:

²Radhika

Former-Assistant Professor

Arni University Himachal

Pradesh

India

E-mail:

radhika.jaryal786@gmail.com

Reviewing editor:

Dr Jaymund M. Floranza

Catanduanes State University

Philippines

¹Lecturer Degree College

Thanamandi Rajouri

India

Disclosure statement

No potential conflict of interest

was reported by the

author(s).

Citation information

Cite this article as: Shah, A.H., & Radhika. (2024). An increasing tendency of unemployment among educated youth, which is harmful to society, special reference to India. *Pedagogical Research and Development*, 3(1), 423-427. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo>.

**AN INCREASING TENDENCY OF
UNEMPLOYMENT AMONG EDUCATED
YOUTH, WHICH IS HARMFUL TO
SOCIETY, SPECIAL REFERENCE TO
INDIA**Anzar Hussain Shah¹, Radhika²

Abstract: Extended unemployment among youth has been linked to lower levels of pleasure and work satisfaction as well as other forms of mental illness. Youth without jobs claim to feel more alone in their communities. Youth who are not in any organization or the workforce are unable to learn new things or enhance their skills. Communities with substantial levels of unemployment are more likely to have restricted employment options, poor-quality housing, fewer opportunities for recreation, restricted access to public transit, and a government that seems disinterested in education. Generating employment for youths is a big difficulty across the world, which has been worsened by the worldwide economic downturn. In this larger global perspective, via this study consider the factors affecting on employment and unemployment in India, the country with the world's biggest youth generation. Poverty and a lack of human capital pose significant challenges for young educated Indians.

Keywords: Educated youth, Technology, Society, Wages, Mental illness

1.1 Introduction

Unemployment is not merely an economic concern; it is the root of practically all other difficulties that people and nations face, including economic, political, social, educational, psychological, emotional, cultural, ethnic, and religious issues. One of the most prevalent types of unemployment among urban and rural populations is educated unemployment. A young person experiencing this kind of unemployment may not be able to obtain employment observing matriculation, graduation

2024 The Author(s). This open access article is distributed under a Creative Commons Attribution (CC-BY) 4.0 license.

Journal Link: <http://kmf-publishers.com/prd/>

post-graduation, or occasionally even after Ph.D. holders. Young males typically work part-time jobs in rural and metropolitan regions, whereas their female counterparts typically work for themselves. Even though a high percentage of young rural women work in agriculture, rural men are turning to jobs outside of agriculture. The educated youth of India face many difficulties, there are several potential reasons why educated people are unemployed, but the most prevalent one is a lack of employment options. This can also occur in situations where there are many applicants but few job openings and a scarcity of companies. There has been a troubling era of widespread joblessness among young educated people. Graduates and postgraduates even Ph.D. holders are bumbling around from job to job in search of employment. In addition, these problems have a direct impact on the nation's economic growth, which in turn raises the rate of unemployment or underemployment. This paper is concerned with youth unemployment and education. There are several reasons for youth unemployment. The most commonly proposed reason, however, is that young people are unemployed because they are unskilled, and they require skills because they are untrained and lack of relevant skills which are required for jobs. As a result, assigning a prominent role to education in addressing the youth unemployment problem has become popular.

1.2 Technology and Unemployment

Technology impacts unemployment this kind of structural unemployment is crucial. Technological progress generally involves the reduction of human involvement through the development of labor-saving "mechanical-muscle" equipment or more efficient "mechanical-mind" procedures (automation). Although new technologies both create and destroy jobs, young workers are more likely than older workers to lose their jobs owing to automation since they tend to work in industries and occupations that are likely to automate (ILO 2020b). Technologies are also enabling the creation of new types of work and job interactions that are not governed by existing legal systems.

"C:\Users\HP\Desktop\images technonology.jpg"

1.3 Unemployment, Challenges for the Educated Youth

Social welfare measures such as the minimum wage can have an impact on the condition of the population, although the impact varies depending on the amount of unemployment in society at the moment. Experienced workers, who are often young, are prepared to accept lesser pay because employment provides them to gain experience. Concerning the employed group, the unemployed group displayed poorer levels of psychological well-being and life satisfaction, as well as higher levels of anxiety, sadness, and loss of behavioral/emotional control. Although youths are working for meager pay, they are not satisfied with their pay and continue to consider themselves as

2024 The Author(s). This open access article is distributed under a Creative Commons Attribution (CC-BY) 4.0 license.

Journal Link: <http://kmf-publishers.com/prd/>

unemployed. For India in recent years, there has been an increase in the unemployment rate, as well as a convergence of the unemployment rate among states. The slowdown in job creation and loss in total employment in the manufacturing sector, as well as structural shifts in the economy, appear to be driving up the unemployment rate.

Unemployment among youth people and mental health. Work not only serves as a person with cash rewards and opportunities for friends and social relations, but it also plays a vital role in the individual's sense of fulfillment and self-worth. Nowadays, things in the field of employment and labor market are fairly difficult, particularly for young people who graduate from universities every year, "coming out" in the labor market full of aspirations and ambitions for the future and eventually confronted with the problem of unemployment. As a result, unemployment is a significant psychological stressor. After foremost, unemployed people are those who want to work but are unable to do so, either because a job is not available or because an employer does not ask them to work. Unemployed people have reduced self-esteem; they feel rejected by society, which leads to feelings of hostility toward society. In rare situations, it may manifest as psychosomatic difficulties or lead to alcoholism and substance misuse, as well as participation in antisocial groups and other hazardous actions.

https://media.springernature.com/lw685/springer-static/image/art%3A10.1186%2Fs13033-020-00395-2/MediaObjects/13033_2020_395_Fig4_HTML.png

<https://cdn.statcdn.com/Infographic/images/normal/20014.jpeg>

2.1 Finding and suggestion

Figured out unemployment types, and impacts on increasing rate of unemployment either directly or indirectly. Disguise Unemployment, Structural Unemployment, Seasonal Unemployment, Vulnerable Unemployment, Technological unemployment, and Cyclical Unemployment concerning all mentioned types. Employment prospects in these places can be enhanced by concentrating on rural development programs, such as modernizing agriculture, developing rural infrastructure, and providing skill training for rural industries. Rural economies can also be strengthened by supporting decentralized industries and rural entrepreneurship. Teach young people sophisticated and technical skills. To the rural areas to address the issue, improvements to the government laws, support for independent contractors, modifications to the educational system, and adjustments to industrial practices can all be made.

3.1 Conclusion

Globalization has made unemployment among educated young men a key aspect. In this piece, I look at the tactics and experiences of young men without jobs across in India. The majority of these men grumble about "just passing the moment" (doing "time passes") in deteriorating universities and colleges. The "problem" of teenage unemployment is thoroughly discussed in this paper, along with the different policy solutions that have been proposed, such as active labor market policy and programs for education and training. It highlights the need for sufficient labor market data, policy oversight, and program assessment to help young people find more and better-quality jobs, and it provides particular advice and suggestions for this age group in industrialized, developing, and transitional countries. The study examines the nature of the youth labor market and how it compares to the labor market for other workers while analyzing the traits, causes, and effects of young unemployment. It examines minimum salaries in addition to the critical function that education and

training institutions play. The paper outlines tactics for getting governments, businesses, and labor unions involved in combating teenage unemployment and offering alternatives.

References

- Evans, J., & Shen, W. (2010). Youth employment and the future of work. Council of Europe Publishing. http://pjp-eu.coe.int/documents/1017981/1668233/YK10_Youth_employment.pdf/6640c44d-e46c-42c8-bd29-e382c3b29c16
- Kaufman, J. A., Salas-Hernández, L. K., Komro, K. A., & Livingston, M. D. (2020). Effects of increased minimum wages by unemployment rate on suicide in the USA. *J Epidemiol Community Health*, 74(3), 219-224.
- Jallade, J. P. (1987). Youth unemployment and education. In *Economics of Education*, Pergamon, 166-172.
- Jeffrey, C. (2010). Timepass: Youth, class, and time among unemployed young men in India. *American Ethnologist*, 37(3), 465-481.
- Mitra, A., & Singh, J. (2020). Structural change in employment and unemployment in India. *Sustainable Development Goals: An Indian Perspective*, 129-138.
- O'higgins, N. (2001). Youth unemployment and employment policy: A global perspective. O'Higgins, (2001).
- Rajvanshi, S., Saxena, S., & Vermax, P. (2019). Incidence of Unemployment Among Educated Youth. *International Journal of Applied Marketing & Management*, 4(1)
- Salaria, V., & Shah, A. H. (2022). Analysis of the Effects of Coronavirus on Businesses and Educated Youth. *Journal of Positive School Psychology*, 6429-6435.